

1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition to sydnones : reaction revisited-role of HBr in the transformation of 3-arylsydones into 3-aryl-5-methyl-2-oxo- Δ^4 -1,3,4-oxadiazolines

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Conversion of 3-arylsydones into 3-aryl-5-methyl-2-oxo- Δ^4 -1,3,4-oxadiazolines was carried out at different reaction conditions using bromine and acetic anhydride to find an unambiguous evidence for the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition mechanism and to detect the role of HBr.

3-Phenylsydnone **1** undergoes one-pot ring conversion to 3-phenyl-5-methyl-2-oxo- Δ^4 -1,3,4-oxadiazoline **3** in presence of acetic anhydride and bromine¹. We have reported² the one-pot synthesis of more such compounds by ring conversion of 3-arylsydones. The mechanism as suggested¹ involves 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of acetic anhydride to the intermediate compound 3-phenyl-4-bromosydnone **2** (Scheme 1). A mention has also been made by Stansfield³ that 3-phenylsydnone undergoes hydrolysis by the liberated HBr, to give phenylhydrazine and this could be an intermediate in the formation of 1,3,4-oxadiazolin-2-one **3**. The fact that such oxadiazolin-2-ones were prepared from phenylhydrazine derivatives^{4,5} must have led to the concept of formation of phenylhydrazine. However, phenylhydrazines do not yield these oxadiazolines with bromine in acetic anhydride. Moreover, this proposal is in contradiction to the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition mechanism. This ambiguity made us to think of reinvestigating the reaction. It may be mentioned here that the sydnone ring opens to give hydrazine with HCl only in presence of water¹. The interesting feature of this conversion is that, though it is one-pot synthesis, it is a two-step reaction carried out *in situ*. The advantage of acetic anhydride playing a dual role, as a solvent for bromination in the first step and also a dipolarophile in the second step, has led to a facile and convenient one-step conversion. Now, our approach was to isolate the intermediate 4-bromo-3-arylsydnone **2** and then subject it to 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition with acetic anhydride, and this addition would be in absence of HBr (Scheme 1).

The 4-bromo-3-arylsydones **2** prepared according to the literature method⁶ were heated with acetic anhydride at 60° (one-pot conversion takes place at 60°). The addition did not take place and compounds **2** were recovered unchanged. On boiling this solution to 140°, the evolution of brown

fumes, possibly of acetyl bromide, was observed and the solution on dilution with water yielded the products, which were identical to compounds **3**. The reaction was a slow process (3–4 h), but the yields and purity were comparable to the one-pot procedure. In another experiment, a mixture of 4-bromo-3-arylsydones **2** and acetic anhydride was

Scheme 1

heated at 60° in presence of a few drops of HBr for ~0.5 h and this reaction also afforded compounds 3 (Scheme 1).

The facile addition of Ac₂O as a dipolarophile at 60° is probably facilitated by HBr which readily polarizes the carbonyl group, while this addition is retarded in absence of HBr and this explains why the addition of Ac₂O to the intermediate 4-bromo-3-phenylsydnone requires vigorous conditions (140°). However, these additions would go according to the mechanism as reported earlier (Scheme 1).

It may be concluded that HBr only accelerates the polarization of acetic anhydride and hence decreases the time for completion of the reaction, but it does not hydrolyze the sydnone ring. These results show further evidence for the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition mechanism and that there is no interaction of HBr with the sydnone ring. With the help of stepwise reactions we have tried to define the role of HBr in this conversion. The cycloaddition of other anhydrides with

4-bromo derivative 2 is being tried and the work is in progress.

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